

APPLICATIONS OF INVARIANT GRAPHS IN GLOBAL CONSTRAINTS

¹Tamanna Kumari, ²Kamal Kumar, ³Richa Agarwal

Department of Mathematics

^{1,2}Baba Mastnath University, Rohtak

³KIET Group of Institutions, Delhi-NCR, Ghaziabad

Email: tamannasepkumari@gmail.com, kamalkumar4maths@gmail.com,
richa.agarwal@kiet.edu

Principal Author: Kamal Kumar

Corresponding Author: Richa Agarwal

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ABSTRACT

The catalogue of global constraints is reviewed, focusing on the graph-based description of global constraints. A number of possible enhancements are proposed as well as several research paths for the development of the area.

INTRODUCTION:

The Term “Global Constraint”. The term global constraint originally appeared in the late 80ies in a thesis [81] dealing with house floor-plan design problems. A global constraint “rooms must fill the house” was incorporated into a generator of house floor-plans. Later on, the term global constraint was reused at the European Computer Research Centre, with a specific constraint taking into account the interaction between several all-different constraints for handling orthogonal Latin squares problems [4]. In [23], Bessi`ere and Van Hentenryck proposed several definitions of the notion of globality. They introduced the notion of “semantic globality (expressiveness), operational globality (quality of filtering), and algorithmic globality (computational efficiency of the filtering)”. As they mention, “globality is often discussed in an operational context with a consistency notion in mind” (i.e., globality refers to some aspect of the filtering).

Aim and Organisation of the Article: This article has two complementary aims regarding the field of global constraints: – To review the work already done with the catalogue [9] and to provide a first generic filtering scheme combining existing and new techniques based on graph properties. – To make a series of suggestions for advancement of the field. They are interspersed in the next sections and have

one of the following forms: • Proposed Enhancements (PE) suggest ways to improve specific parts of the catalogue of global constraints. Their purpose is to draw attention to general questions related to potential uses of global constraints in different contexts. • Research Paths (RP) draw attention to key issues related to the synthesis of code for global constraints. They typically are long-term goals.

This article aims to stress the fact that global constraint can be used beyond filtering. For this reason, the term global constraint should be understood here as an expressive and concise condition involving a non-fixed number of variables. This informal definition does not make any assumption about the potential use of a global constraint. Indeed, defining the concept of global constraint in terms of its potential uses simply “dries up” this concept.

Here's a brief review of a paper on graph theory titled "An Introduction to Graph Theory and Its Applications" by Richard J. Trudeau.

The paper begins by introducing the basics of graph theory, including the definition of a graph and its components, such as vertices and edges. It then delves into various types of graphs, such as directed and undirected graphs, weighted graphs, and complete graphs.

The paper also covers some of the fundamental concepts of graph theory, such as degree, path, and connectivity. It then explores more advanced topics, including graph colouring, planarity, and graph algorithms.

One of the strengths of this paper is its clear and concise explanations of complex graph theory concepts. The author presents the material in a way that is accessible to readers with little background knowledge in mathematics or computer science.

The paper also includes several real-world applications of graph theory, such as in social network analysis, transportation planning, and circuit design.

Overall, "An Introduction to Graph Theory and Its Applications" is a well-written and informative paper that provides an excellent overview of the field of graph theory. It is a great resource for students and researchers looking to learn more about this fascinating area of mathematics

The Area of Global Constraints: Current Status. Global constraints were initially introduced in industrial solvers [31, 65] for solving recurring problems in dedicated application areas. From an early time, global constraints have been used for their strong pruning power thanks to efficient specialised filtering algorithms that take advantage of the structure of the constraints they consider (see for instance, the filtering algorithms proposed for the all-different constraint [29, 71, 55, 24, 66, 56, 59]). More recently, it became clear that global constraints are not only useful for their deductive power, but that they also have a central role to play in modelling languages for problem solving [45], in local search

[46], in symmetry breaking [68], in visualisation tools for debugging constraint programs [77], in linear programming tools [49] or in deriving efficient heuristics [41] based on their internal status.

The Essence of Constraint Programming: An Engineering or an Academic Field? Global constraints are recognised as a mean to accelerate the convergence between Constraint Programming and Operations Research [60]. As a consequence of this current convergence, a common opinion is that Constraint Programming is becoming a sub-field of Operations Research: Constraint Programming provides a collection of new techniques that can be added or combined with, for instance, classical techniques from Linear Programming or Metaheuristics. By adopting this point of view, Constraint Programming is reduced more to an engineering field than to a basic science field with a core question to address [48]. However, the “Holy Grail” [38, 44] was quite clear right from the beginning of Constraint Programming: specify a problem in a declarative way, and let the machine solve it in an efficient way. Actually, no paradigm usually attached to Operations Research has addressed such a question. On one hand, many efficient solution methods have been developed in Operations Research, but they often are very specialised to handle one given problem. On the other hand, the declarative modelling aspect distinguishes Constraint Programming from systematic solution approaches of Operations Research, such as Linear Programming. For both practical and theoretical reasons, the core question of Constraint Programming should be pursued: – From a practical point of view, the question of the applicability of Constraint Programming has been raised by one of the main providers of Constraint Programming tools at the CP’2004 conference [67]: as more and more efficient ad-hoc methods are involved, the technique gets more and more difficult to use in practice. In a sense, Constraint Programming *gc.tex*; 3/10/2006; 17:43; p.2 **Global Constraint Catalogue: Past, Present and Future 3** is joining established fields (e.g., logic, linear programming, algorithmic, group theory) whose techniques require a strong expertise only to be used. – From a theoretical point of view, the question is to come up, not just with efficient solution methods dedicated to specific problems, but with a theory allowing to automatically generate efficient solution methods from the explicit description of the problems.

The article is organised as follows: Section 2 gives the motivations behind the catalogue of global constraints [9]. – Section 3 presents the description of global constraints in terms of graph properties as well as in terms of automata. It also suggests research paths related to this second representation. – Section 4 summarises the results obtained so far related to the systematic graph property-based filtering. It shows how to reformulate a global constraint into a satisfaction problem according to its graph description. Then it presents a first filtering for this reformulation, by computing tight bounds on graph parameter values [17] and by using graph invariants [10]. *gc.tex*; 3/10/2006; 17:43; p.4 **Global Constraint Catalogue: Past, Present and Future 5** – Section 5 sketches a natural continuation of this work. It illustrates how to filter by enforcing graph properties according to the parameter bounds, and shows how to tighten those bounds for specific graph classes. Then, we present the generic graph-based

filtering scheme, which puts together all the elements introduced in Sections 4 and 5. Finally, we show how to retrieve existing filtering algorithms for global constraints such as all different and proper forest, with this scheme, and how to adapt it in the context of CP(Graph) [32]. – Section 6 gives several research paths, beyond filtering, related to the graph-based representation of global constraints. – Section 7 concludes.

Motivations

This Section presents our motivations for an explicit description of the meaning of global constraints. A current trend in the field of global constraints is to use natural language to describe the meaning of a global constraint, and then, to work out a specialised filtering algorithm. Describing all potential global constraints with this approach is an endless task, when one considers the many ways of combining global constraints. This is even worse if, in the long term, we aim at providing other services such as visualisation [77], explanations [76], soft global constraints [63, 16, 80], learning implied global constraints [20], or specialised heuristics for each global constraint. These considerations motivate the use of a composable mathematical language for explicitly describing the meaning of global constraints. The CP(Graph) framework [32], for instance, proposes a restricted form of second order predicate calculus. However, when it comes to filtering algorithms, this model is not used anymore.² For such a reason, Prolog was restricted to Horn clauses for which one had a reasonable solving mechanism. Through this example, we want to stress the fact that a declarative description is really useful only if it also provides some hints about how to deal with that description.

GRAPH-BASED DESCRIPTION

We first proposed a description of global constraints in terms of graphs satisfying some graph properties that are given by formulae. This choice was influenced by the following observations:

² One could perhaps use a system like MONA [43] for getting a constraint checker in the context of CP(Graph). *gc.tex*; 3/10/2006; 17:43; p.5 6 N. Beldiceanu, M. Carlsson, S. Demassey and T. Petit – The concept of graph has its roots in the area of mathematical recreations (see for instance L. Euler [36], H. E. Dudeney [33], E. Lucas [57] and T. P. Kirkman [52]), which was somehow the ancestor of combinatorial problems. – In one of the first books introducing graph theory [19], C. Berge presents graph theory as a way of grouping apparently diverse problems and results. This was also the case for global constraints. – The parameters associated with graphs are concrete and concise (e.g., the number of arcs, the maximum size of connected components,). Moreover, a lot of results about graphs can be expressed in terms of graph invariants involving various graph parameters, that are valid for specific graph classes. In essence, formulae are a kind of declarative statement that is much more suited for creating a knowledge data base in combinatorics than algorithms. In fact, as we will see in Section 5.1, quite often significant parts of filtering algorithms can be reinterpreted as a compiled form of a graph invariant I , which enforces the validity of I . – Finally, it is well known that graph theory is an important

tool [58] with respect to the development of efficient filtering algorithms [71, 72, 73, 75, 59, 50, 14, 79, 69]. The question of how to automatically generate efficient code from the description of a problem was already identified as the core question by forerunners in Constraint Programming like J. Pitrat [64] and J.-L. Laurière [54]. Both promote an approach based on meta-programming but did not address the question of the relation between the combinatorial aspect of constraints and graph theory. In Operations Research, we can cite a work of P. Hansen related to this article [42]. He addresses the question of the automatic generation of graph invariants that can potentially be used in branch and bound methods.

The study of the content of database graph invariants for global constraints is an important area of research in database theory and graph theory. In particular, it is concerned with the development of techniques for characterizing and analysing the invariants of graphs that are useful for representing global constraints in databases.

This report presents a database of about graph invariants for deriving systematically necessary conditions from the graph properties-based representation of global constraints. This scheme is based on invariants on the graph characteristics used in the description of a global constraint. A SICStus Prolog implementation based on arithmetic and logical constraints as well as on indexical is available.

A global constraint is a constraint that applies to the entire database, rather than to individual tables or records. Examples of global constraints include unique key constraints, referential integrity constraints, and business rules that apply to the entire database.

Graph invariants are properties of graphs that are preserved under certain transformations, such as relabelling nodes or edges, or taking subgraphs. Examples of graph invariants include the number of nodes, the number of edges, the degree sequence, and the spectrum of the adjacency matrix.

The study of the content of database graph invariants for global constraints involves developing techniques for identifying and characterizing the graph invariants that are relevant for representing various types of global constraints. This can involve developing algorithms for computing graph invariants efficiently, as well as techniques for analysing the relationships between different graph invariants.

One important application of this research is the development of efficient algorithms for enforcing global constraints in databases. By characterizing the relevant graph invariants for different types of constraints, it is possible to develop algorithms that can check whether a given database satisfies the constraints, or that can modify the database to satisfy the constraints.

Uses of invariant graphs in global constraints

Invariant graphs are a useful tool in the design and implementation of global constraints in constraint programming. Invariant graphs can be used to specify complex constraints that involve multiple

variables, by representing the constraints as a graph structure where nodes correspond to variables and edges represent constraints between the variables.

Efficient constraint propagation: Invariant graphs can be used to perform efficient constraint propagation, by defining local consistency rules that propagate constraints along the edges of the graph. This can lead to faster constraint solving, as the propagation of constraints can quickly eliminate large portions of the search space.

Incremental propagation: Invariant graphs can be used to perform incremental constraint propagation, by maintaining a dynamic representation of the constraint graph and updating it as new constraints are added or removed. This can allow for more efficient constraint solving, as the solver can avoid re-computing the entire constraint graph each time a constraint is added or removed.

Constraint learning: Invariant graphs can be used to learn new constraints from data or examples, by analyzing the structure of the graph and identifying patterns or structures that correspond to useful constraints. This can lead to more efficient constraint solving, as the solver can automatically learn new constraints that are specific to the problem being solved.

Constraint reformulation: Invariant graphs can be used to reformulate complex constraints into simpler, more manageable constraints. By identifying sub-graphs of the constraint graph that correspond to simpler constraints, the solver can replace the original constraint with a set of simpler constraints that are easier to propagate and reason about.

Conclusion:

Overall, invariant graphs are a powerful tool in the design and implementation of global constraints in constraint programming, and can be used to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of constraint solving in a wide range of applications.

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